

Research Article

Development And Validation of New RP-HPLC Method For the Simultaneous Estimation of Sofosbuvir And Velpatasvir In Combined Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, accurate, precise, specific and sensitive reverse phase-HPLC method has been developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. The chromatographic separation was performed on the Discovery C18 column (250mm×4.6mm, 5µm particle size), using a mobile phase of OPA (0.1%): Acetonitrile = 50:50 (v/v), at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min in an ambient temperature of 25°C with the detection wavelength of 260nm. The retention times of Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir were 2.47 min and 3.32 min respectively. The linearity was performed in the concentration range of 100-600 µg/mL, 25-150 µg/mL each of Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir with a correlation coefficient of 0.998 and 0.999 for Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir respectively. The proposed method has been validated for specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision and robustness were within the acceptance limit according to ICH guidelines and the developed method can be employed for routine quality control analysis in the bulk and combined pharmaceutical dosage form.

INTRODUCTION

Sofosbuvir [1-2] is a direct acting antiviral medication used as part of combination therapy to treat chronic Hepatitis C, an infectious liver disease caused by infection with Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). Treatment options for chronic Hepatitis C have advanced significantly since 2011, with the development of direct acting antivirals such as

sofosbuvir. As a pro-drug nucleotide analogue, sofosbuvir is metabolized into its active form as the antiviral agent 2'-deoxy-2'-α-fluoro-β-C-methyluridine-5'-triphosphate (also known as GS-461203), which acts as a defective substrate for NS5B (non-structural protein 5B). NS5B, an RNA-dependent RNA polymerase, is essential for

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the transcription of Hepatitis C viral RNA and for its high replicative rate and genetic diversity. Sofosbuvir and other direct acting antivirals are therefore very potent options for the treatment of Hepatitis C, as they exhibit a high barrier to the development of resistance. Sofosbuvir (**Fig.-1**) has a molecular mass of 529.45 g/mol, molecular formula of $C_{22}H_{29}FN_3O_9P$ and has IUPAC name is Propan-2-(2S)-2-([(S)-[(2R,3R,4R,5R)-5-(2,4-dioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-1-yl)-4-fluoro-3-hydroxy-4-methyloxolan-2-yl]methoxy}(phenoxy)horyl]amino}propanoate.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Sofosbuvir

Velpatasvir [3] is a direct-acting antiviral medication used as part of combination therapy to treat chronic Hepatitis C, an infectious liver disease caused by infection with Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). HCV is a single-stranded RNA virus that is categorized into nine distinct genotypes, with genotype 1 being the most common in the United States and affecting 72% of all chronic HCV patients. Velpatasvir acts as a defective substrate for NS5A (Non-Structural Protein 5A), a non-enzymatic viral protein that plays a key role in Hepatitis C Virus replication, assembly, and modulation of host immune responses. Treatment options for chronic Hepatitis C have advanced significantly since 2011, with the development of Direct Acting Antivirals such as velpatasvir. Notably, velpatasvir has a significantly higher barrier to resistance than the first generation NS5A inhibitors, such as ledipasvir and daclatasvir, making it a highly potent and reliable alternative for treatment of chronic Hepatitis-C. Velpatasvir (**Fig.-2**) has a molecular mass of 883.01 g/mol,

molecular formula of $C_{49}H_{54}N_8O_8$ and has IUPAC name is (2S)-2- {[hydroxy(methoxy)methylidene]amino}-1- [(2S,5S)-2-(17-{2-[(2S,4S)-1-[(2R)-2- {[hydroxyl (methoxy)methylidene]amino}-2-phenylacetyl]-4-(methoxymethyl)pyrrolidin-2-yl]-1H-imidazol-5-yl]-21-oxa-5,7-diazapentacyclo[11.8.0.0^{3,11}.0^{4,8}.0^{14,19}]henicosa-1(13),2,4(8),6,9,11,14(19), 15,17-nonaen-6-yl)-5-methylpyrrolidin-1-yl]-3-methylbutan-1-one.

Figure 2: Chemical structure of Velpatasvir

LITERATURE:

Some analytical methods have been reported for the determination of sofosbuvir [4-10] in pharmaceutical dosage forms and biological samples. But only few analytical methods using chromatography [11-26] have been reported for the simultaneous determination of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir in combined dosage forms. The present study concentrates on simultaneous RP-HPLC method and its validation in a novel fixed dose combination tablet of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir following the ICH directions.

EXPERIMENTAL

INSTRUMENTATION

HPLC system (Waters) with binary HPLC pump (model number 2695), PDA detector (model number 2998) and degasser with 10 μ L injection loop were used. The chromatographic data was processed by Waters Empower2 software. Electronic balance ELB 300 and Digisun pH meter were used.

MATERIALS

The reference samples of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir (API) were obtained from M/s. Sun pharma limited, Ahmadabad, India. The branded formulation (tablets) (Velpanat tablets containing Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir) manufactured by M/s. Natcopharma limited, Hyderabad was procured from the local market. HPLC grade methanol, acetonitrile and analytical grade orthophosphoric acid were obtained from M/s. Rankem Chemicals Ltd, Mumbai, India. Milli-Q water dispensed through a 0.22 μ filter of the Milli-Q water purification system (Millipore, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) was used throughout the study.

Chromatographic Conditions

The chromatographic separation and analysis of selected drug combination were worked out on a Discovery C18 column (250mm \times 4.6mm, 5 μ m particle size). The mobile phase used is a mixture of OPA (0.1%): Acetonitrile = 50:50 (v/v), at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. Mobile phase filtration using 0.45 μ m membrane filter was done and 10 min sonication was performed. The column temperature is 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C while analyzing. The analyte elution was monitored using a photodiode array detector set at 260 nm. 10 μ L is the injection volume.

Preparation of stock standard and tablet sample

About 200 mg of sofosbuvir and 50 mg of velpatasvir were accurately weighed and transferred into a 50 mL clean dry volumetric flask containing 30 mL of the diluent. The solution was sonicated for 10 min and then volume was made up to the mark with a further quantity of the diluent to get a concentration of 4000 μ g/mL of sofosbuvir and 1000 μ g/mL velpatasvir (Stock solution). A mixed working standard solution was further prepared by diluting the above stock solution to obtain a concentration of 400 μ g/mL of sofosbuvir and 100 μ g/mL of velpatasvir.

Twenty tablets of the commercial sample of 'Velpanat' were weighed and finely powdered. An accurately weighed portion of powdered sample equivalent to 200 mg of sofosbuvir and 50 mg of velpatasvir was transferred into a 50 mL volumetric flask containing 30 mL of the diluent. The contents of the flask were sonicated for about 10 min for complete solubility of the drugs and the volume made up with a further quantity of the diluent. Then, this mixture was filtered through a 0.45 μ membrane filter. Further, 1 mL of the above filtrate was pipetted into a 10 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up with the diluent.

Method Optimization

Parameters of chromatography such as time of retention, peak tailing, theoretical plates count, and resolution were determined to optimize the method. For that, trials are carried out - different mobile phase ratios and different stationary phase types, with temperature difference, values of pH and flow rate. On this basis method is employed to separate sofosbuvir and velpatasvir from themselves and also from stress degradants, discovery C18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) column having temperature 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C was selected which gave good symmetric and sharp peaks. Based on less analysis time, peak response, peak symmetry and column efficiency, and mobile phase used is a mixture of OPA (0.1%): Acetonitrile = 50:50 (v/v), at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min using photodiode array detector, a wavelength of 260 nm was selected as detection wavelength. The chromatographic parameters optimized exhibit a good peak shape, resolution and a good number of theoretical plates. The typical chromatogram of velpatasvir and sofosbuvir by the developed method is presented in **Figure-3**.

Figure 3: Chromatogram of standard solution of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir

METHOD VALIDATION

Validation was performed by referring to ICH guidelines. HPLC Suitability, linearity, selectivity, accuracy, sensitivity, precision, specificity and robustness were determined.

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

Study of System suitability established by six consecutive injections with the same working standard solutions. The number of theoretical plates was found to be > 2000, USP tailing was < 2 and USP resolution is above 2. The values for the system suitability parameters of the method, as presented in Table- 1, are within acceptance limits.

Table-1: System Suitability of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir

S. No.	Sofosbuvir			Velpatasvir		
	Area	USP Plate Count	USP tailing	Area	USP Plate Count	USP tailing
1	4205215	6915	1.37	1728204	8432	1.34
2	4199444	6687	1.41	1698342	8432	1.34
3	4189975	6687	1.41	1674356	8166	1.32
4	4205289	6742	1.39	1719675	8152	1.30
5	4213456	7358	1.33	1728202	8642	1.30
6	4225677	6839	1.41	1719436	8403	1.31
Mean	4206509			1711369		
Std. Dev.	12182.9			21168.3		
% RSD	0.29			1.24		

SPECIFICITY:

Specificity is the ability to determine unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. The specificity of the method was performed by injecting blank solution, placebo solution and working standard solutions of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir separately. No interfering peaks were observed at the retention times of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir. Hence, the method is specific for the simultaneous determination of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir.

LINEARITY AND SENSITIVITY

Linearity was done by preparing standard solutions of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir at five concentration levels. The linearity of detector

response for sofosbuvir and velpatasvir was verified by prepared solutions in concentration range 100-600 µg/mL and 25-150 µg/mL respectively. Peak area of each sample against respective concentration of analytes was found to be linear. Correlation coefficient of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir are 0.998 and 0.999. Linearity results were presented in Table-2. This method's sensitivity was represented as limits of quantification (LOQ) and detection (LOD). Determining detection and quantitation limits is based on the signal-to-noise ratio with 3:1 & 10:1. Determined LOD values and LOQ values for sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were shown in Table-2.

Table-2: Regression Analysis and Sensitivity of Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir

Parameter	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasvir
Linearity ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	100-600 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	25-150 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Equation of regression ($A = SC + I$)	$y = 10172x + 5976.5$	$y = 16839x + 24692$
Slope (S)	10172	16839
Intercept on Y-axis (I)	5976.5	24692
Regression coefficient (R^2)	0.998	0.999
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.44 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.33 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	1.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

A = Peak area of analyte; I = analytes' concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)

PRECISION AND ACCURACY

For precision studies, the same standard solutions of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were injected 6 times into the HPLC system on the same day. The percentage RSD values calculated for peak areas of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were less than 0.6 %

(Table-3) indicating the precise assay with the developed HPLC method. For accuracy, the percentage recovery was calculated for both active ingredients. The results (Table-6) are acceptable with good percent recovery.

Table 3: Results of repeatability of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir

S. No.	Sofosbuvir			Velpatasvir		
	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	4136808	6815	1.36	1676927	8433	1.34
2	4166672	6787	1.42	1674769	8432	1.33
3	4166672	6683	1.41	1659724	8165	1.35
4	4146929	6755	1.39	1665289	8154	1.31
5	4136794	7359	1.34	1681692	8644	1.30
6	4171736	6837	1.43	1669206	8405	1.32
MEAN	4154269			1671268		
SD	15980.6			8077.2		
% RSD	0.4			0.5		

Intermediate Precision:

Six replicate injections of the same dilution were analyzed on two different days for verifying the variation in the precision. The % RSD of the results for sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were found

to be 0.2 and 0.3 respectively, which are within acceptable limit of ≤ 2 . Hence, the method is reproducible on different days. This indicates that the method is precise. The results are shown in the Table 4 & 5.

Table 4: Results of Intermediate precision of sofosbuvir

S. No.	Average area (n=6)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
Day 1	4221403	6784	1.25
Day 2	4221401	6696	1.36
Overall average	4221402		
SD	10005.1		
% RSD	0.2		

Table 5: Results of Intermediate precision of velpatasvir

S. No.	Average area (n=6)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
Day 1	1726580	8554	1.32
Day 2	1726582	8495	1.28
Overall average	1726581		
SD	5707.9		
% RSD	0.3		

Recovery Test

Further evaluation of the accuracy of the method was carried through recovery test. Recovery test was determined by means of the standard addition method. The recovery experiments were performed by adding sofosbuvir and velpatasvir standards at three concentration levels to the

placebo for three times. The recovery test results are summarized in Table 6. Hence, the obtained results indicated that the developed HPLC method was accurate enough for simultaneous quantitative evaluation of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir. There was no interference noticed from the common excipients of the tablet.

Table 6: Results of recovery experiments of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir

Preanalysed amount (µg/ml)		Spiked amount (µg/ml)		% Recovered	
Sofosbuvir	Velpatasvir	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasvir	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasvir
200	50	100	25	99.13	99.06
200	50	100	25	99.58	99.50
200	50	100	25	99.10	100.36
200	50	200	50	99.04	100.57
200	50	200	50	99.02	100.53
200	50	200	50	99.10	100.16
200	50	300	75	99.77	101.25
200	50	300	75	99.25	100.43
200	50	300	75	99.91	100.23
			MEAN	99.32	100.25
			SD	0.304	0.569
			%RSD	0.34	0.63

Robustness

Under the slightly varied chromatographic conditions (mobile phase's flow rate ± 0.1 mL/min & temperature in the column $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), sofosbuvir

and velpatasvir peaks were well separated and there was no significant change in the system suitability parameters (Table-7 and Table-8), which illustrated the robustness of the method.

Table 7: Robustness study for sofosbuvir

Condition	Mean area	% assay	% difference
Optimized	4213158	99.65	-----
Flow rate at 0.9 mL/min	4210341	99.04	0.61
Flow rate at 1.1 mL/min	4213265	99.79	0.14
Mobile phase:			
• Buffer-acetonitrile (55:45)	4214210	100.11	0.46
• Buffer-Acetonitrile (65:35)	4214231	100.15	0.50
Column Temperature:			
• at 25°C	4210335	99.03	0.62
• at 35°C	4212844	99.59	0.06

Table 8: Robustness study for Velpatasvir

Condition	Mean area	% assay	% difference
Optimized	1722424	99.81	----
Flow rate at 0.9 mL/min	1723566	100.03	0.22
Flow rate at 1.1 mL/min	1722856	99.97	0.16
Mobile phase:			
Buffer-acetonitrile (55:45)	1722652	99.65	0.16
Buffer-Acetonitrile (65:35)	1722243	99.23	0.58
Column Temperature:			
at 25°C	1718839	99.02	0.79
at 35°C	1723646	100.05	0.24

Stability of formulation solution:

The sample solutions were analyzed at 0 h (comparison sample) and after 24 h (stability sample) by keeping at ambient room temperature. Stability was determined by determining %RSD

for the formulation sample solutions. The sample solution injected after 24 h by keeping at room temperature (30°C) did not show any appreciable change. The deviation in the assay was not more than 2 and the results are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Stability data of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir

Drug	%Assay at 0 h*	%Assay at 24 h*	Deviation
Sofosbuvir	99.56	99.01	0.55
Velpatasvir	100.05	99.85	0.20

*n=6 for each parameter

DISCUSSION ON THE RESULTS

A Discovery C18 (4.6 x 250 mm; 5 µm) was selected as the stationary phase for separation of both drugs and detection was carried out at 260 nm. Initially, reverse phase liquid chromatography separation was attempted using various ratios of methanol and water and acetonitrile and water as the mobile phases, in which both the drugs were not eluted properly, and the resolution was also poor. Further trials were also performed to optimize the organic content of mobile phase phosphate buffer. The retention times were found to about 2.473 and 3.316 min for sofosbuvir and velpatasvir respectively.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, a new simple, precise and accurate HPLC method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir in tablet dosage form. In this method, a Discovery C18 (4.6 x 250 mm; 5 µm) was selected as the stationary phase. A 50:50

v/v mixture of phosphate buffer and acetonitrile was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Under the optimized conditions, the retention times obtained for sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were 2.473 and 3.316 min respectively. This HPLC method was validated as per the ICH guidelines. In this method, the number of theoretical plates is above 2000, tailing factor is less than 2 and RSD of peak area is less than 2, which indicates that the optimized method met the limits of system suitability parameters. The linearity ranges obtained for the drugs are sofosbuvir and velpatasvir showed in 25-150 µg/mL and 100-600 µg/mL respectively. The percent mean recovery values of sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were found to be 99.32 and 100.25% respectively and it showed that the proposed method is accurate. RSD values of repeatability and intermediate precision were ≤2 and hence the method is precise. The lowest values of LOD and LOQ as obtained by the proposed HPLC method

indicate that the method is sensitive. The solution stability studies of method indicate that sofosbuvir and velpatasvir were stable up to 24 h. Chromatographic conditions were deliberately changed slightly to check the robustness of the method and the results showed the reliability of the method as no appreciable changes in the results were observed.

The proposed method has some benefit over the earlier reported methods. Both the drugs were eluted with a simple mobile phase with good resolution. The retention times of the drugs obtained in this method were short. The short run time shows the speed of analysis which enables more number of samples to be analyzed per unit time. The proposed RP-HPLC method is precise and accurate and can be used for routine quality control analysis for simultaneous determination of Sofosbuvir and Velpatasvir in their tablet dosage forms.

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